

Imagining Municipalities as Data Fiduciaries

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Abstract

City governments in the United States require a data governance framework that simplifies the current patchwork of domain-specific privacy rules, while preserving their ability to use data in service of the public good. This paper investigates the utility and feasibility of designating municipal governments “data fiduciaries” that are required to act in their residents’ best interests when processing their data. I draw on information privacy and fiduciary law literature and consider several real and hypothetical examples of data processing decisions in cities to illustrate how establishing municipal data fiduciary requirements would improve on existing data protection standards. Fiduciary duties square with the image of the city a “data steward” and offer a coherent cognitive schema for residents, city employees, and judges to hold cities accountable for responsible data processing. I argue that a process-oriented fiduciary duty of care would require cities to engage the public in high impact data processing decisions, and a fiduciary duty of loyalty would require officials to act in the exclusive interest of the data provider.

Keywords – information fiduciaries, fiduciary law, data governance, local government, cities

1 Introduction

Most functions of local government create or use data. Consider the following scenarios.

The New York City Police Department’s Domain Awareness System connects private video feeds of public spaces in downtown Manhattan to police officers’ phones, giving them better situational awareness when responding to incidents (Levine, Tisch, Tasso, and Joy 2017). Privacy advocates argue this type of general surveillance can create a chilling effect on peoples’ behavior (Díaz 2019).

The New York City Department of Health and Mental Hygiene likewise receives data feeds from private entities across the City for surveillance purposes. Hospitals share

epidemiological data on symptoms from emergency room visits to allow the department to identify and contain disease outbreaks early in their spread (Heffernan et al. 2004).

The New York City Taxi and Limousine Commission (TLC) receives data from taxi and ride-sharing companies to check whether they obey safety regulations. Recognizing a public interest in the data, the TLC published pseudonymized trip records. Media outlets were able to link these ostensibly anonymous data to celebrities’ taxi rides, causing public embarrassment over paltry tips and trips to strip clubs (Gayomali 2014).

All three examples represent instances of New York City government accepting sensitive data from private sources and analyzing it to perform their operational mandates. Although these types of information take a similar technical form as digital data, their function and social effects are far from uniform. The data maintained by municipal government represents a variety of instruments of state power and have a range of epistemic utility. By the same token, they risk unique types of privacy harm. An implicit, socially optimal boundary lies between the potential benefits and potential harms of data processing. The goal of good data governance should be to locate that boundary, and state it explicitly as policy.

Civil liberties-focused privacy advocates, civic innovation-focused open data advocates, and efficiency-focused analytics champions are often at odds on the appropriate governmental use of this data. Existing privacy frameworks concern how sensitive types of personal data, such as name, date of birth, address, and race, are collected and shared. In the United States, which has no comprehensive data protection framework and lacks a “data subject” model, privacy laws are domain-specific. In addition, once a government agency collects data, it often faces few restrictions on how it may process it. These conditions motivate a search for a new, practicable framework that

local governments can deploy when making decisions about how to collect, use, and disclose personal data.

Many local officials and civic leaders are making meaningful strides to this end. Barcelona has declared its citizens' "data sovereignty" to be the foundation of its smart city strategy (Bria 2018). Many cities have voluntarily certified against What Works Cities' benchmarks for effective and transparent data management (Bloomberg Philanthropies 2020). Several cities have joined the international Cities Coalition for Digital Rights, which advocates for transparent and non-discriminatory use of data (Cities for Digital Rights 2020).

While these initiatives are important, they lack the institutional durability of the law. I suggest that fiduciary law holds promise for formalizing good data governance principles in a way that outlast any particular political administration. In this paper, I argue that the "information fiduciary" concept can and should be applied to local governments. I explore how the fiduciary duties of care and loyalty would require local governmental agencies to approach data processing more thoughtfully, and provide an appropriate schema for public administrators to imagine themselves as data stewards.

2 Cities as Data Fiduciaries

Fiduciary law concerns relationships which rely on trust and good faith. Fiduciaries address the agency problem, which arises when an individual (the "principal" or "beneficiary") places their trust in another (the "agent" or "fiduciary") to make decisions on their behalf (Frankel 2018).

The application of fiduciary responsibilities to data processors has become popular in the information privacy literature. It answers the frustration that unscrupulous data processing can violate straightforward notions of trust, even if technically permitted by law. In 2014, Jack Balkin discussed how imposing fiduciary duties on companies like Facebook and Google would curtail their ability to profit from the surveillance and manipulation of their users' data. The "information fiduciary" designation would legally require companies to act in users' "best interests" with respect to the personal data they entrust to the platforms (Balkin 2016). Jonathan Zittrain (2014, 2018) has also been a proponent of information fiduciaries, arguing that, if put into practice, the concept would formally prohibit large platform companies from using sensitive data to interfere with democratic elections. Recent proposals for "data trusts" (Delacroix and Lawrence 2018) and "data cooperatives" (RadicalxChange 2020) advocate for fiduciary intermediaries to leverage the collective bargaining power of many individuals' data to negotiate more advantageous terms of services with Internet companies.

Lina Khan and David Pozen (2018) question whether fiduciary duties are coherent principles for companies with business models organized around behavioral advertising. The primary loyalty of businesses built on extractive data processing is to shareholders, which is irreconcilable with information fiduciaries' proposed loyalty to platform users. This critique, however, may be moot in organizations whose primary purpose *already* resembles a fiduciary duty to act in the best interest of their constituencies – namely, government agencies.

Public authorities and fiduciaries both act on behalf of others. Although the common law fiduciary framework has developed primarily with respect to private agents – corporate directors and trustees; doctors and lawyers – several legal thinkers have recently theorized the applicability of fiduciary duties to governmental bodies. Evan Fox-Decent (2012) argues that the state derives its power to enforce laws not from the consent of the governed, but rather its fiduciary obligations to the public. Evan Criddle (2010) argues that when regulatory agencies exercise discretion beyond their legislated mandates, their actions are subject to fiduciary duties.

While the merits of "information fiduciaries" and public sector fiduciaries have each received substantial scholarly attention, this is the first paper to attempt to bridge the two.

All levels of government implicate an array of privacy risks whenever they collect data. Why do cities warrant special attention? Because cities are "where people are, and hence where their data is, in great abundance" (Rubinstein 2018, p. 107). Local government is the level of government individuals interact with most visibly and frequently. Municipal employees such as teachers, police officers, and social workers are the faces of services society has deemed "public goods." As they increasingly rely on data and computational technology to enact policy and provide services, it is incumbent on cities to prove their bona fides as trustworthy data stewards. Fiduciary duties, which are rooted in normative principles of trusteeship and good governance, aesthetically fit the data stewardship mandate. The next two sections explore how the specific duties of care and loyalty could be applied in practice.

3 Duty of Care

3.1 Process-Oriented "Care"

The history of America's first cities can be traced to private corporations, such as the Virginia Company of London, which were formed by shareholders to profit from developing colonial communities. As property owners trading in private markets, cities act in their capacity as private corporations. Max Schanzenbach and Nadav Shoked (2018) argue that this history obligates municipal officials to abide by a corporate fiduciary duty of care when buying

or selling municipal assets. They recommend these transactions be subject to the process-oriented duty of care established in the Delaware/Model Business Corporation Act (MBCA), which “focuses judicial review on the process officials used to enter large transactions” (p. 610). Applied to cities, the Delaware/MBCA is more of an instrument for good governance than a tool for opportunistic litigation. Taxpayers who feel the city has committed to a decision against their best interest are not eligible for damages typical in violations of fiduciary trust. Instead, this standard would give residents the ability to appeal to courts to block or reverse decisions made without adequate consideration and public consultation.

Importantly, the standard does not provide oversight on the *outcome* of municipal decisions themselves — that remains the prerogative of elected municipal officials, for whom residents have recourse at the ballot box. Rather, it focuses accountability on the *process* officials used to make such a decision, which addresses the “more normatively pertinent question: whether the city exercised its power in a proper fashion” (p. 632). The more exceptional the decision — for example, the more it departs from routine decision-making, the greater its financial consequences, and the more it falls outside of the existing expertise of the decisionmakers — the greater caution and deliberation required.

3.2 Accountability for Important Data Processing Decisions

Susan Crawford (2018) extends this thinking to urban data sharing projects. Cities have a fiduciary duty to consider the long-term implications of allowing private companies to collect data on its citizens. The procedural duty of care would require them to “show their work” and clearly articulate how deals that trade citizens’ data, including Sidewalk Labs’ plan to install a smart city sensor network in a Toronto neighborhood, are consistent with the city’s values (Crawford 2018, ppg. 11). Both Crawford’s and Shanzenbach and Shoked’s analyses pertain to trading municipal assets, when cities clearly act in their corporate capacity in the private market. But the principle can be extended to decisions regarding municipal data governance more broadly.

Evan Criddle (2010) argues that government bureaucracy represents a network of nested fiduciary relations. The political executive (in local government, the mayor or city manager) is a fiduciary to the public, responsible for using their management powers and political influence to execute the public will. Administrative agencies, as unelected rulemakers and law enforcers, are likewise bound by fiduciary duties, but rather than obey the “ephemeral public will,” they must fulfil their fiduciary obligations by acting “*deliberatively* and reasonably in promoting the public welfare” (p. 442, emphasis mine).

A government agencies’ use of data is rarely prescribed by legislation, giving municipal officials a wide latitude for discretion in data management decisions. Extending the fiduciary duty of care in the Delaware/MBCA would require a city to act “*deliberatively* and reasonably” when deciding whether and how to implement technologies to monitor public space, share previously collected administrative data between city agencies, or prioritize service delivery with statistical models. An agency which fast-tracks procurement for a surveillance system to aid law enforcement might raise a red flag and prompt taxpayers to seek judicial review. However, installing a business intelligence application on an existing tax records database may be ineligible for review on the basis that the change is routine and incremental. An exception might also be made for a data collection initiative explicitly authorized by legislation, given that the legislative process *already* requires robust public engagement and deliberation.

3.3 Example: Public Engagement on the Census’s Differential Privacy Decision

The U.S. Census Bureau’s decennial count is a privacy invasive data collection activity, but Census data produces enormous value through primary and secondary uses. When research demonstrated risks to respondents’ privacy associated with publishing the Census’ ostensibly anonymized data products, the Bureau decided to apply differential privacy methods to its 2020 data publications (Abowd 2018). Differential privacy adds “noise” to data that prevents re-identification; this comes at a tradeoff, however, resulting in less accurate data. The degree of this tradeoff — how much accuracy is exchanged for how much additional privacy protection — is mathematically precise. To determine its optimal value, the Bureau conducted extensive public engagement, beyond what is required in routine agency rulemaking. It solicited comments from the data’s users, who shared 700 impact statements detailing how the differentially private dataset affected their work (U.S. Census Bureau 2018). It engaged with the research community through several conferences and workshops, and experts appeared before the House of Representatives’ Committee on Oversight and Reform to debate its impact (U.S. Congress 2019).

In short, the Census Bureau demonstrated extensive procedural care in its determination of the socially optimal boundary between its data’s usefulness and its risk to personal privacy. This is unsurprising: the Census is the nation’s oldest and perhaps most used data product. The shape of electoral politics in the United States is contingent on its results. The Bureau’s decisions about its data are naturally recognized as decisions of public import.

By contrast, many data collection and processing initiatives in local government take place out of public view. As cities collect more data and rely on data processing for policy and

operational decisions, important data processing decisions should be subject to the same best practices enjoyed by more well-trodden areas of policymaking. A procedural duty of care subjecting exceptional data processing decisions to judicial review would mandate it.

4 Duty of Loyalty

A duty of loyalty obligates the fiduciary to act in the sole interest of the beneficiary. Loyalty can be both a proscriptive duty, requiring the fiduciary to *abstain* from activity against the exclusive interest of the beneficiary, as well as a prescriptive duty, requiring the fiduciary to take *positive action* to advance its beneficiary's interest (Miller and Gold 2015). Applied to governmental data processing, a duty of loyalty could permit local government agencies to process private data to the extent that it produces the best outcomes for the represented individuals, while prohibiting data processing that does not directly serve their interests.

4.1 Loyalty vs. Privacy Rights

Khiara Bridges (2011, 2017) contends that poor people in the American legal system do not have privacy rights. Privacy rights for the indigent are not, as many suggest, just diluted or difficult to exercise – as a legal matter, they do not exist. The legal doctrine asserting the government's paternalistic obligation to intervene in the lives of the formerly incarcerated or social welfare recipients supersedes their claims to personal privacy. Even the most aggressive data protection regime is unlikely to change this.¹

Proposals for data protection which require individuals to give consent to process their data, or pool the collective data rights, are premised on the *existence* of data rights which, according to Bridges, may not be an accurate assumption where government is involved. Fiduciary obligations, on the other hand, are *relational*, concerning normative responsibilities *between* parties. They do not depend on the existence of a personal data right to be a check on harmful data processing. In this way, a government's fiduciary loyalty to an individual's data could be privacy-enhancing without conflicting with the state's responsibility, in some circumstances, to take actions that individuals have not explicitly consented to.

In Bridges' example of Medicaid recipients seeking prenatal care in public hospitals, a duty of loyalty might allow a hospital administrator to inquire about a woman's sources of income to assess her eligibility for related social services, but prohibit inquiries about immigration status that create data records making her vulnerable to deportation. Loyalty might permit general video surveillance of a public tourist

site that is a known target for terrorism incidents, but forbid a police department from maintaining a database of individuals with suspected gang affiliations.

Or not. If, when soliciting public input (as required by the city's procedural duty of care), the affected community and consulted experts unequivocally express that collecting income data on poor women seeking prenatal care, or conducting general surveillance of a high-risk public space, is not in the best interest of the cohort whose data is being collected, the government would receive a clear signal of their preferences and be obligated to act loyally to them. What constitutes "loyalty" is not predetermined and fixed; it is a moving target. The point is that, for any case of high-profile data processing, the government considers who is benefitting and how, and if the answer is unclear because it pertains to a contestable norm or a non-routine use of power, it asks.

4.2 Example: Balancing Privacy with Agility when Rolling out Universal Pre-K in NYC

Consider the rollout of New York City's Universal Pre-Kindergarten (UPK) program. In 2014, the City's commitment to provide free pre-kindergarten services to every child represented a massive operational undertaking, starting with the task of marketing the program and enrolling eligible four-year-old students. The Mayor's analytics team combined data from the City's health and human services agencies with data from Experian, the credit reporting company: both datasets included a list of signals indicating if a given household included a four-year-old eligible for the program (Crawford, Lader, and Smith 2015). The analysis generated a list of likely households, which were in turn targeted by enrollment specialists with mailers and phone calls. It also allowed these enhanced enrollment efforts to stop pestering parents once the child enrolled.

The City decided that the tradeoff between an individual's informational privacy, as represented by the inferences made from their Experian credit profile, and the benefit from enrolling in free childcare was an acceptable exchange. Alternatively, if the city had used the same credit profiles from Experian to identify individuals violating the tax code, one might assume public outcry and a fallout in public trust. Acquiring and analyzing this data, the City decided, was justified by the UPK's social value. Even though compliance with tax laws, on the whole, is also socially valuable, using the *same* analytical methods on the *same*

¹ How to restore the poor's privacy rights, of which information privacy is only a subset, is a worthwhile discussion. But if we accept Bridges' contention that this is a political project requiring activism to shift the prevailing social, cultural, and economic order, it is outside the scope of a data governance framework for municipal agencies, and the scope of this paper, to address.

data would likely trigger alarm. Levying fines against an individual would likely be considered *disloyal*.

In this case, decisions on the appropriate tradeoff between privacy and the benefits of data processing were made according to the instincts of the government employees who staffed the project. A duty of loyalty would formalize those instincts as a legal obligation.

4.3 Loyalty to Whom?

Local governments are often required to make decisions which prioritize certain parties, calling into question the feasibility of a loyalty test in many scenarios. For instance, following recent protests against police across the country, the New York State legislature repealed Section 50-a of the state's civil rights law, which protected police disciplinary complaints from public release. Legislators determined that the publication of those records provided a tool to hold police officers accountable; it was therefore in the public's best interest to publicize them. A federal judge disagreed, and blocked the City of New York and NYC Civil Liberties Union from publicly releasing the data, citing the potential for harm to police officers (Feuerherd 2020).

In cases where the interests of an individual represented in data are different than the interests articulated by a vocal group of advocates, or in cases where multiple individuals with conflicting preferences are represented in a single data policy decision, whom should the government favor? Under a strict definition of data "loyalty," a municipality might interpret disclosing records of police disciplinary history as disloyalty to the officers represented in that data, despite the public interest in that data. This creates the very conflict of interest that the test of fiduciary loyalty is supposed to address in the first place.

One way of resolving competing claims to loyalty would appeal to a fiduciary *governance* mandate, where loyalty is not owed to a particular individual but rather a more abstract entity such as a set of normative values or a specifically stated purpose (Miller and Gold 2015). This would resemble the fiduciary duties held by charitable trusts, which are not bound to the interest of particular individuals, but rather to the set of goals governing the trust. Alternatively, the government might subject itself to a "demonstrable partiality standard of loyalty," where in cases of conflicted loyalties, it documents its decision options, projects their impacts on competing beneficiaries, and documents their justification for pursuing a certain course of actions (Miller 2014, p. 219). In other words, the government may exercise discretion, but would need to clearly "show its work."

It is clear that a duty of loyalty cannot be applied as a blunt instrument and would require additional rules and principles defining how to interpret "loyalty" in various contexts, given the complexities of governing cities. But despite these

shortcomings, a duty of loyalty to act in the best interest of the data provider at least *conceptually* refocuses the aim of government to treat its residents as the direct beneficiaries of the data they provide, rather than public bodies subject to a wide latitude of information extraction and data-based interventions. In this way, it starts to enshrine a normative notion of the "data subject" without requiring the decades of activism and legal precedent that have codified data subjects into European law.

5 Implementation Considerations

According to the argument that cities are *already* corporate entities subject to fiduciary duties, courts might be persuaded to interpret existing cases of governmental data misuse under fiduciary law. A more probable route would be to codify data fiduciary responsibilities in local legislation (Shoked 2018). If this seems farfetched, consider that representatives of the New York City's Chief Privacy Officer testified in support of state privacy legislation that would enact fiduciary responsibilities on online service providers (N.Y. State Senate 2019). It is not inconceivable that they, and local officials in other forward progressive municipalities, would elect to apply similar standards to themselves.

From facial recognition technologies to the integration of social welfare datasets, cities "are experimenting with diverse solutions that reflect key differences in how their political leaders weigh... the tradeoffs between maximizing openness and minimizing privacy risks" (Rubinstein, 2018, pp. 161-162). This trial-and-error approach is necessary to achieve consensus on socially desirable boundaries between protecting residents' privacy while maximizing public benefit through the analytic use and disclosure of data. Christena Nippert-Eng (2010) calls this process "boundary play," which can draw out both consensus and tensions in individuals' and society's conceptions of privacy and data processing norms. In the same way that progressive policy at the local level has instigated federal law on policies such as anti-smoking measures, living wage laws, and gun regulations, cities have the opportunity to "play" with data processing policies in order to "(1) fill gaps in existing federal and state privacy law or (2) where such laws exist, raise the floor established by federal or state constitutional or statutory rules" (Rubinstein 2018, p. 170).

6 Conclusion

Currently, a patchwork of data protection laws chills some good data collection and data processing initiatives in local government because of administrative overhead while allowing some bad initiatives to be cleared through a matter

of administrative gymnastics. The data fiduciary standard shifts the locus of government data work from paperwork back to the individual.

Fiduciaries responsibilities offer a well-developed cognitive framework for delegated trust, sound discretion, and good stewardship (Alexander 2000). Applying fiduciary mandates to municipal data processing could be an effective way of giving legal purchase and conceptual coherence to the image of the city as a “data steward.” Imagining themselves as data fiduciaries provides a heuristic for policymakers and bureaucrats to conceive of their responsibilities when collecting and using data, and a pathway for the public to hold them accountable. For government employees, this could provoke a cognitive shift in the image of personal data, not as the digital exhaust of the administrative state, but as an important municipal asset carrying a duty of loyalty owed to the person it represents.

In concert with the extensive rules, regulations, and oversight that already govern the behavior and decisions of public servants and elected officials, the data fiduciary framework delivers a practical set of values based on the social effects of data. It calls for a recognition that data is not purely epistemic information representing attributes about a person, but a growing instrumental force in local politics and public administration. The fiduciary standard demands the agent be accountable to their beneficiary through transparency about the actions they take, elevating decisions about data use to the same level of non-digital policy decisions, subject to similar oversight and accountability mechanisms.

Daniel Solove (2001) writes that while Orwell’s “Big Brother” is the prevailing literary metaphor for data privacy concerns, a more fitting analogy is found in Franz Kafka’s *The Trial*, where data processing is indicative of “a more thoughtless process of bureaucratic indifference, arbitrary errors, and dehumanization, a world where people feel powerless and vulnerable, without any meaningful form of participation in the collection and use of their information” (p. 1398). Imagining local government as a data fiduciary with a procedural duty of care to solicit public input on impactful data processing decisions, and a duty of loyalty to act in the best interest of the data provider, pushes cities to humanize data processing in government bureaucracies, allowing their residents to more meaningfully participate in and benefit from the urban data ecosystem.

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